

Book Reviews

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Stream and river scientists, managers, and enthusiasts will be excited to dig in to the second edition of *Rivers of North America*, edited by Delong, Jardine, Benke, and Cushing. This is a handsome – and hefty (1088 pages) – book that provides detailed descriptions of 156 rivers that drain 22 distinct geographic regions in North America. The spatial coverage is comprehensive,

with chapters spanning the northernmost rivers of the Arctic, warm and humid tropical rivers of southern Mexico, and nearly everything in-between. Perhaps more aptly considered a second ‘volume’, the focus of this book is on mid-sized rivers that were only briefly mentioned or not mentioned at all in the first edition, which tended to highlight the larger rivers in North America. Thus, the second edition provides a wealth of new material that very much complements the first, and - in my opinion - is worthy of occupying a prominent place in your library, perhaps even snuggled between the first edition and its companion, *Rivers of Europe*.

The book begins with an introductory chapter that covers a bit of general background about rivers and a more detailed account of the book’s approach. Here, the editors provide a high-level overview of the multiple subsections that are common to all

subsequent chapters (e.g., Physiography and Climate, River Biodiversity and Ecology), including helpful maps that illustrate geographic boundaries of the large river basins and physiographic provinces, as well as example graphics that introduce the reader to regional variation in precipitation, runoff, and evapotranspiration. This chapter does a nice job of setting the stage for subsequent chapters and providing a scaffolding that imbues a high degree of consistency, both among chapters and between the first and second editions.

Each primary chapter takes us on a journey of multiple rivers within a geographic region, and is co-written by experts – predominantly scientists and a few engineers – that study, manage, or work to protect these rivers. Chapters begin with a broad geographic description of the region, often providing a history of human habitation, including a brief sketch of early and present-day Indigenous communities and European settlers. One is reminded that each of these regions has a unique human history, and that rivers have always been at the center of human activity, subsistence, and culture. Next, each chapter describes the physiography of the region, highlighting key aspects of geology, including physiographic provinces that underlie the focal river basin(s). In addition, chapters provide general information about regional climate (i.e., temperature, amount and types of precipitation), as well as a subsection dedicated to basin landscape and land use, reporting dominant terrestrial ecoregions and forest types and a description of past and present land use. Together, these introductory sections paint a comprehensive ‘template’, which is leveraged in subsequent descriptions of individual focal rivers.

Each chapter then describes multiple (ranging from 4 to 9) focal rivers, presenting much more granular information about physiography, climate, and land use, and knowledge about the river’s geomorphology, hydrology, chemistry, and biodiversity/ecology. The level of detail in these sections varies greatly among chapters, revealing large differences in the current state of knowledge. For instance, while there has been substantial research and monitoring in places such as the Colorado River Basin or the Gulf Coast Rivers of the Southeastern US, much less is known about rivers of Mexico or those in remote regions of the Canadian Arctic and sub-Arctic, including large portions of the Mackenzie, Nelson, and Churchill River Basins which drain an area roughly one-third the size of the European continent! These sections also contain a brief discussion of ‘Human Impacts and Special Features’, as well as one on ‘Areas of Need for Research and Management’ – a new feature in the second edition. Finally, chapters contain beautiful photos of the focal rivers, literature cited, and one-page ‘snapshots’ of each focal river that includes a high-quality map, climatic and runoff data, and a brief list of major geographic, physical, and biological attributes. A careful perusal of any individual chapter will leave the reader with a foundational understanding of the rivers, and their variation, in the region or basin.

The final chapter of the book provides a general overview, synthesizing basic physical and biological characteristics among the major basins, and presenting a few interesting patterns and relationships. Although

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such an endeavor could represent an entire book on its own, this chapter does a nice job of comparing 'vital statistics' of rivers (e.g., basin size, relief, discharge, etc.) and highlighting various aspects of biodiversity and ecosystem processes. Among other things, we learn that non-native fishes represent a much higher proportion of total species richness in the Columbia, Pacific US, and Colorado River Basins than in, for example, the Ohio, MacKenzie, and Southeastern US River Basins. The final section of this chapter is focused on restoration and recovery of North American rivers, first outlining major threats (e.g., pollution, fragmentation, non-native species) and then presenting key challenges and opportunities for mitigating these threats. I found this chapter decidedly optimistic, with the message that there is historic precedent for reversing negative trends and rehabilitating rivers, and that we have a collective choice about making this happen moving forward.

There are many aspects of this book that will be valuable to dedicated readers. First, a serious reading of the book (which should not be done over a short period of time!) represents a master class in 'river macrosystems'. Although most of us spend our time and effort working or playing in a limited number of rivers, the rich descriptions and photos presented in this book leave the reader with a strong sense of how these ecosystems vary across large spatial scales and why. Second, the structure of each chapter forces the reader, in a good way, to recognize just how much the 'valley rules the stream', and provides a wealth of insight into how human activities have modified this relationship. Third, the book will provide a useful reference for those moving to work on rivers in a new

region, heading to a job interview in an unfamiliar landscape, entering graduate school in river science, or developing research projects and teaching modules that require a continental-scale perspective. It certainly got my wheels turning with respect to research and teaching ideas.

Finally, in the course of reviewing this book, a few general thoughts emerged. First, it's clear that much of what we know about North American rivers comes from the efforts of a relatively small group of scientists and agencies clustered around major universities and population centers. Consequently, some river basins have received substantial attention and continue to be studied and monitored closely, while others remain somewhat 'off the radar'. In large areas of the continent (especially parts of the Arctic and Mexico), ongoing or planned anthropogenic activities including oil drilling or new hydroelectric projects are likely to continue with little background information or surveillance. It is worrying that we will know little about the consequences of these actions. In addition, even in well-studied regions, it seems that there are simply too many rivers and too little resources to keep our collective fingers on the pulse. It is heartening, however, that public awareness about the importance of rivers is growing, as are citizen science groups and support for non-profit conservation organizations. There is hope!

Second, I was left with the feeling that there is a vast amount of information based on long-term monitoring efforts that is underreported and underutilized. Given how much time, effort, and money goes into collecting these datasets, one hopes that we can work towards dedicating the resources to collate and synthesize these data to

better understand and manage these ecosystems into the future. Growing interest and capabilities in data science are likely to help. Last, I was struck by how abbreviated most of the 'Ecosystem Process' sections were throughout the book. Although monitoring efforts by agencies and research groups have led to a rudimentary understanding of biodiversity in most of the focal rivers, much less is known about ecosystem processes, or the emergent relationships between biodiversity and ecosystem functions. Once again, there is reason to be optimistic as new advances come online in deployable sensor technology, remote sensing products, integrative ecosystem modeling efforts, and eDNA metabarcoding. I am hopeful that a future edition will show progress in these areas.

So, whether you're an academic, an agency or non-profit scientist, a student, or even an avid traveler interested in rivers, I encourage you to buy a copy of this book. You'll find that it is really different than your other books about rivers – and can serve as a fantastic reference text. Just don't read it too fast.

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South Cottonwood Creek, Montana USA. Photo by Samuel J Larkin